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The Impact Of Climate Change On Food Security In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The current global challenge of climate change has continued to influence agricultural activities particularly in developing countries that rely mostly on rain-fed farming. The ugly situation of climate change has been argued to have had the potentials of exacerbating food insecurity in Nigeria by different scholars. Some believed that the food security goal of Nigeria may not be achieved without tackling the problem of climate change first. However, research studies in the context of climate change and food security have produced mixed results. Thus, this study investigates the impact of climate change on food security in Nigeria using quarterly data from 1986Q1-2023Q4. The robust least squares (RLS) method was employed to analyze secondary data on relevant variables, comprising climate change, population growth, food exports, food price inflation, food security, climate change, food exports, governance quality, and agricultural infrastructure. The study sources data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletins, the Transparency International data bank, and the World Development Indicators (WDI) database. The findings of the study show that climate change has a significant negative impact on food security, with a coefficient of -2.8086 and a probability value of 0.0098. Also, population growth and governance quality have a significant negative effect on food security, as shown by their coefficients of -63.4940 and -0.9490, and probability values of 0.0000 each. Again, food export and food price inflation exert insignificant negative impact on food security, with coefficients of -0.1092 and -0.0213, and probability values of 0.2380 and 0.3445 respectively. However, only agricultural infrastructure shows a significant positive impact on food security in Nigeria, with a coefficient of 0.0053 and a probability value of 0.0000. Based on the findings, the study recommends the adoption of climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies, population control measures, regulating food export to maintain sustainable food sufficiency, stable food price control measures, improving governance quality and institutional structure, and sustainable agricultural infrastructure investment.

Keywords: Food Security, Climate change, Food price inflation, Population Growth Rate, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural sector in Nigeria has numerous obstacles that affect its output, notwithstanding its economic contributions in the past and now. The poor land tenure systems, low irrigated farming levels, climate change and land degradation, low technology, high production costs and inefficient input distribution, poor funding, significant post-harvest losses, and difficult market access are few of these problems. Due to these difficulties especially, agricultural output and food security has been hindered, which has reduced the sector's GDP contribution (FAO, 2022).

Climate change is defined as a shift in the climatic condition that lasts for several decades or longer, and may be detected statistically through variations in the mean and/or variability of its parameters. It refers to

the long-term trends in temperature, humidity, air pressure, wind, precipitation, air particle count, and other metrological element measurements in a particular area. Climate change could also be defined as the significant modification of natural atmospheric environmental factors, which is accompanied by unfavourable reactions such as changes in overall and unprecedented weather patterns, which might involve anomalous precipitation temperature, density, cloud appearance, or uncommon rain yield (IPCC, 2007). The current unpredictable pattern of rainfall in Nigeria has attributed to poor agricultural productivity and food insecurity due to its attendant negative effects.

The oceanic activities, biotic processes, variations in the amount of solar radiation that the planet receives, plate tectonics, volcanic eruptions, and changes made to the natural environment by humans are the main causes of climate change. The defrosting of ice in the Arctic and Antarctic due to these later effects is currently generating global warming, and "climate change" is frequently and mostly caused by the consequential effects of activities by humans. A climate change that is caused by global warming has a significant impact on seasonal cycles, ecosystem predictability and stability. These factors have a negative impact on total agricultural productivity, but particularly on water production and food security. The planting's seasonal cycles are always disrupted by variations in patterns of precipitation. Also, late or very early rain exhibits substantial effect on planting and farming businesses. All these frequently result in an odd planting and replanting order for crops (FAO, 2009). Rainfalls that currently arrive later in the day usually prolong the dry season and delays rain-fed planting season. The disruptive nature of climate change extends beyond the consequences of intense weather, making rainfall unfeasible and altering rainfall yields. It has a potential impact on the availability of healthful food for both human and animal consumption. Food costs could also rise as a result of climate change, making it extra harder for the poor to get food (FAO, 2013).

The average yearly variation and trend of rainfall across Nigeria within recent decades, has shown the presence of several inter-annual alterations that have caused extreme weather events like droughts and floods in various parts of the nation at different times, both wet and dry season periods. A number of facets of living including poverty, environmental degradation, and food security tend to be influenced by climate change. The world's hunger is also increasing due in large part to climate change and its fluctuating nature (FAO *et al.* 2023).

In West Africa, desertification poses threat to about 35% of the land, particularly in the northern region where poverty has been made worse by degradation of land and climate change. For instance, there is serious risk of desert incursion in Northern part of Nigeria, where sand dunes are turning into typical geological features in States like Katsina, Borno, Sokoto, Yobe and Jigawa. This poses danger to agricultural production as it buries significant amounts of arable land, and rangelands for grazing. Also, the second-highest tropical rainforest in the globe, making up around 30% of the world's total rainforest cover and serving as a biodiversity reservoir, is found in the African wet tropics, yet agricultural productivity is still at its low ebb in the region. This low productivity could be attributed to Climate change, which is causing countries in the region to lose their land and forests (FAO, 2016). The agricultural sector in Africa is primarily reliant on rainfall, with small-scale agriculturalists using irrigation systems sparingly and producing little during the dry season. According to UN predictions, in 25 years from now, Africa's lack of access to water for consumption and agricultural activities could be a leading factor contributing to strife and bloodshed. For instance, the disappearance of 90% of Lake Chad has resulted in the eviction of tens of thousands of persons; and serious damage to rural farming, animal grazing, and fisheries.

The weather patterns, utilization of sufficient inputs, and the supply of suitable land are some of the variables that affect agricultural output in this part of the world. Agribusiness' productivity is dependent on meteorological factors. Nigeria may find it difficult to grow sufficient food for its own needs as the country's environment gets ever more severe for stable agricultural practices. Also, with regular droughts, erratic weather patterns, and increasing temperatures, crop yields could decline and worsen food security in Nigeria. As the tradition of nomadic farming is the most common model of livestock production in Africa, drought-related land degradation is making it harder for the pastoralists to access rangeland for

grazing. Due to this, there are now more people migrating, which have caused social unrest and widespread agricultural farm ruin. The difficulties of producing cattle are made even harder by factors like fragmented grazing grounds, and restricted access to water. There have been an increasing number of farmer-herder clashes in numerous African nations, including Nigeria; these have resulted in fatalities and reduced agricultural prod. For example, Mercy Corps estimates that; if farmers and pastoralists in Plateau, Nasarawa, Kaduna, and the Benue States all lived in peace, Nigeria could experience an annual gain in macroeconomic advancement of up to 13.7 billion dollars (SAHEL, 2019).

Globally, it is predicted that; in the case of high CO₂ emissions, climate change will lower fish supplies by 7.7 percent, and profits by 10.4 percent by 2050. Owing to overfishing and the effects of climate change, the number of fish available in some parts of West Africa may have decreased by as much as 56 to 60 percent. Fish sizes are decreasing as a result of rising sea temperatures, which cause fish stocks to migrate away from equatorial latitudes and toward colder waters. Up to 12 million individuals in sub-Saharan Africa are thought to be employed in the fishing industry, and they could lose their jobs as a result. Food production capacity will be further reduced and food costs will rise as a result of the current problem of a restricted food supply, which is supported by the different effects of climate change, such as decreased crop yields, limited agro-ecological resources, flood and hostilities. Essentially, 83 million individuals in 46 nations, mostly in Africa, are expected to need emergency food assistance. This is a rise of 75% since the SDG of "zero hunger" was established in 2015. Developing mitigation techniques to increase food security in Africa is urgently needed (FEWSNET, 2019).

The existence of climate change and the regularity of its adverse effects pose serious risks to food production in many parts of the globe. Due to the unfavorable impacts of climate change, there is a need for international concern, mitigation initiatives, and support for policies that would limit human activity that contributes to climate change. Climate change which pertains to alterations in the average variability characteristics of the climate that endure for a considerable amount of time, usually several decades or more has constitute a major global concern (IPCC, 2014). Seven of the 10 nations in the world that are thought to be most vulnerable by climate change shocks are in Africa. Nigeria, Somalia, and South Sudan are among the four conflict-affected countries across the globe that are "at risk of famine," according to the 2018 Food Crises Global Report. The food insecurity is caused by a number of variables, but climate change is one of the less discussed ones. Unpredictable rainfall patterns make agricultural productivity uncertain, which limits the amount of food that is affordable, accessible, and available in Nigeria. Even with these obstacles, a small number of African nations are leading the way in creating novel solutions, like implementing climate-smart farming methods to mitigate climate-related issues (Birgit, Conrad & Lars, 2022).

African countries are becoming more concerned regarding the effects of climate change in light of the recent destruction caused by droughts, flooding, desertification, and violence around the continent. A sizable African group attended the 2015 Paris Conference of Parties, or "COP21," which produced the Paris Agreement. As of 2016, 47 African nations had ratified the accord, pledging to implement tangible measures to alleviate and adjust to rising temperatures. Only a small number of African nations, nevertheless, are taking steps to achieve the goals of the pact. It is concerning to note that, as of 2018, according to the Climate Action Tracker, only 3 African nations Ethiopia, Morocco, and South Africa were spearheading the development of policies to achieve the goals of the accord (World Bank, 2019).

Significant proof that global climate change has risen dramatically over the past fifty to hundred years in Africa is presented in the fifth report of the assessment on warming by the IPCC, with implications for the continent's population's food security, livelihoods, and health conditions. For instance, the January 2019 high rainfall that Lagos, Nigeria, saw was unusual because it fell during the dry season. In recent years, similar shifts in conventional seasonal patterns have become more common. A long-term shift in seasonal rhythms brought on by an upsurge in the amount of greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere by burning fossil fuels is just one of the many impacts of climate change (CFS, 2022).

In recent years, devastating flood disasters have affected many African countries. One of the biggest flood catastrophes in Mozambique's history, the year 2000 floods in the Limpopo Valley left up to 650,000

individuals without a place to live and at least 700 dead. The country's economic growth rate was predicted to have slowed by 2.1 percent due to the floods, with an approximate total cost of as much as 20% of gross domestic product. Even now, Mozambique still experiences frequent and severe flooding. About 715,000 hectares of farmlands, or 13% of the nation's total cultivated area, were destroyed by Cyclone Idai in 2019, devastating portions of the country and 500,000 farming families. In addition, the cyclone killed around 500 people and left 1.85 million individuals in need of assistance. The anticipated amount of money needed right now to respond to the cyclone is 282mnUSD (Adesete, Olanubi & Dauda, 2023).

Climate change affects food security in Nigeria by 106% for every unit of variation, highlighting its significant impact on agricultural productivity. Rainfall patterns in the country have become increasingly unpredictable, with more frequent precipitation peaks in recent years. These shifting climate trends have affected Nigeria's entire vegetative zones. Ongoing desertification has forced many herders to migrate from the northern region to the south, leading to frequent clashes with farmers. Additionally, farmers who cultivate the wet plains along the Niger and Benue Rivers are severely affected by recurring floods. These floods have repeatedly damaged food crops, disrupting the seasonal supply of agricultural produce. As a result of climate-related events, certain food items often fail to arrive on time in the market (Adokwe, Oguanobi, & Ugwunna, 2023)

By 2100, agricultural sectors in nations like Zambia, Niger, and Chad may completely lose out as a result of climate change. Furthermore, by 2050, climate change may cost Nigeria, the continent's second-biggest economy, between 6 and 30% of its total gross domestic product, or \$100 billion to \$460 billion. In West Africa, desertification poses a threat to about 35% of her total land mass, particularly in the northern region where impoverishment has been made worse by soil deterioration and climate change. For instance, there is a serious risk of deserts encroachment in Northern part of Nigeria, where sand dunes are becoming typical geological features in States as Kastina, Borno, Yobe, Jigawa and, Sokoto. This poses an imminent danger to agricultural productivity as it puts away significant amounts of arable land and rangelands (DFID, 2023). For farmers growing crops; whose operations rely on the rain-fed, the beginning and end of the rainy season have become less predictable.

The above precarious situation of effect of climate change on agricultural production in Nigeria has led to the quest to identifying the impact of climate change on the quest for food security in the country. Thus, this study seeks to investigate the effect of climate change on food security in Nigeria over the period of 1986-2023.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Concept of Climate Change

Climate change refers to long-term shifts in climatic conditions that persist for several decades or more and can be statistically observed through variations in the mean and/or variability of climate parameters. It encompasses long-term trends in temperature, humidity, air pressure, wind patterns, precipitation, air particle concentrations, and other meteorological elements within a specific region. Additionally, climate change can be defined as a significant alteration in natural atmospheric conditions, often accompanied by adverse effects such as unprecedented weather patterns, irregular precipitation levels, temperature anomalies, cloud formation changes, or unusual rainfall patterns (IPCC, 2007). While weather describes daily fluctuations in atmospheric conditions at a given location, climate refers to the long-term average state of the Earth's lower atmosphere in a particular region.

The primary drivers of climate change include oceanic activities, biotic processes, fluctuations in solar radiation received by the planet, plate tectonics, volcanic eruptions, and human-induced alterations to the environment. The melting of ice in the Arctic and Antarctic due to human activities is a key contributor to global warming, which in turn accelerates climate change. The consequences of climate change, particularly those linked to global warming, significantly disrupt seasonal cycles, ecosystem stability, and environmental predictability. These disruptions adversely impact overall agricultural productivity,

especially food and water production. Irregular precipitation patterns frequently disrupt the planting season, while late or early rainfall negatively affects farming activities. These uncertainties often lead to irregular planting and replanting cycles (FAO, 2008). Additionally, delayed rainfall extends the dry season and postpones planting, further compounding agricultural challenges. Climate change's disruptive effects extend beyond extreme weather events, making rainfall patterns less reliable and affecting overall water availability. This, in turn, threatens the availability of nutritious food for both human and animal consumption. As a consequence, food prices may rise, making it increasingly difficult for low-income populations to access food.

Over the past decades, the annual variation and trends in rainfall across Nigeria have exhibited significant inter-annual fluctuations, contributing to extreme weather events such as droughts and floods across different regions and seasons. Climate change has far-reaching implications for various aspects of life, including poverty levels, environmental sustainability, and food security. Globally, hunger levels continue to rise, in large part due to climate change and its unpredictable nature (FAO *et al.*, 2018).

In this study, climate change is considered in terms of variations in precipitation (rainfall) patterns and their subsequent effects on agricultural production and food security over time. Precipitation patterns therefore, serve as a proxy variable for representing the climatic change.

2.1.2 Concept of Food Security

When everyone, everywhere, has physical and financial access to enough safe, nutrient-dense food that satisfies their dietary needs and food choices for an active and healthy life, there is "food security" (Shaw, 2007).

Over the past decades, as public policy has changed, so too, have concepts of food security (Clay, 2002). The phrase was first used in the middle of the 1970s, when the World Food Conference (1974) conceptualized food security as ensuring the availability and stability of fundamental foods at both the local and global level, as well as their prices.

After focusing on access to food in 1983, the FAO developed a concept of food security that centered on equilibrium among the supply and demand sides equation of the food security:

"Making sure that every individual throughout all times enjoy physical as well as financial access to the fundamental food supplies they require" (FAO, 1996).

The conceptualization of food security analysis has now changed to encompass not only the regional and national levels of accumulation, but also the individual, and family levels. The changing patterns of food security were the main topic of the tremendously significant 1986 World Bank Reports on Poverty and Hunger (Clay, 2002). The World Bank paper established a line of differentiation among two types of food insecurity: transitory food insecurity, which involved times of increased strain brought on by catastrophic events, and chronic (financial crisis or violence) food insecurity which was linked to issues of on-going or structural poverty and low earnings. The Sen's theory of famine (1981), which emphasized the impact of individual entitlements such as labour, commerce, production, and transfer-based resources on access to food, was complementary to this report.

The widely recognized World Food Summit (1996) definition, which takes into account access to food, availability of food, use of food, and food stability, emphasized the multifaceted character of food security. This has made it possible to implement policy solutions that support and restore livelihood possibilities. Livelihood concepts, which were first made popular by scholars like Chambers and Conway (1992), are now essential to the development initiatives of donor agencies. These include risk, management of risk, coping of risk, and vulnerability; they are used more and more in emergency situations. In summary, food insecurity has been analyzed as a social and political construct considering the disappearance of the relationship among food security, starvation, and crop failure (Devereux, 2000).

In this study, food security is seen as the economic status of Nigeria in providing affordable and accessible food to her citizenry at a particular point in time. This includes the sustainability of stable food system to ensure that Nigerians live above acute hunger and abject poverty. The objective of food security in Nigeria is in tandem with the sustainable development goal of eradicating absolute poverty and hunger, and that of African Food security agreement of Maputo, 2003.

2.1.3 Climate Change and Food Security

In West Africa, desertification poses threat to about 35% of the land, particularly in the northern region where poverty has been made worse by degradation of land and climate change. For instance, there is serious risk of desert incursion in Northern part of Nigeria, where sand dunes are turning into typical geological features in States like Katsina, Borno, Sokoto, Yobe and Jigawa. This poses danger to agricultural production as it buries significant amounts of arable land, and rangelands for grazing. Also, the second-highest tropical rainforest in the globe, making up around 30% of the world's total rainforest cover and serving as a biodiversity reservoir, is found in the African wet tropics, yet agricultural productivity is still at its low ebb in the region. This low productivity could be attributed to Climate change, which is causing countries in the region to lose their land and forests (FAO, 2018). The agricultural sector in Africa is primarily reliant on rainfall, with small-scale agriculturalists using irrigation systems sparingly and producing little during the dry season. According to UN predictions, in 25 years from now, Africa's lack of access to water for consumption and agricultural activities could be a leading factor contributing to strife and bloodshed. For instance, the disappearance of 90% of Lake Chad has resulted in the eviction of tens of thousands of persons; and serious damage to rural farming, animal grazing, and fisheries.

The weather patterns, utilization of sufficient inputs, and the supply of suitable land are some of the variables that affect agricultural output in this part of the world. Agribusiness' productivity is dependent on meteorological factors. Africa may find it difficult to grow sufficient food for its own needs as the continent's environment gets ever more severe. Also, with regular droughts, erratic weather patterns, and increasing temperatures, crop yields could decline. As the tradition of nomadic farming is the most common model of livestock production in Africa, drought-related land degradation is making it harder for the pastoralists to access rangeland for grazing. Due to this, there are now more people migrating, which have caused social unrest and widespread agricultural farm ruin. The difficulties of producing cattle are made even more difficult by factors like fragmented grazing grounds, and restricted access to water. There have been an increasing number of farmer-herder clashes in numerous African nations, including Nigeria; these have resulted in fatalities and reduced agricultural productivity. For example, Mercy Corps estimates that; if farmers and pastoralists in Plateau, Nasarawa, Kaduna, and the Benue States all lived in peace, Nigeria could experience an annual gain in macroeconomic advancement of up to 13.7 billion dollars (SAHEL, 2019).

Globally, it is predicted that; in the case of high CO₂ emissions, climate change will lower fish supplies by 7.7 percent, and profits by 10.4 percent by 2050. Owing to overfishing and the effects of climate change, the number of fish available in some parts of West Africa may have decreased by as much as 56 to 60 percent. Fish sizes are decreasing as a result of rising sea temperatures, which cause fish stocks to migrate away from equatorial latitudes and toward colder waters. Up to 12 million individuals in sub-Saharan Africa are thought to be employed in the fishing industry, and they could lose their jobs as a result. Food production capacity will be further reduced and food costs will rise as a result of the current problem of a restricted food supply, which is supported by the different effects of climate change, such as decreased crop yields, limited agro-ecological resources, flood and hostilities. Essentially, 83 million individuals in 46 nations, mostly in Africa, are expected to need emergency food assistance. This is a rise of 75% since the SDG of "zero hunger" was established in 2015. Developing mitigation techniques to increase food security in Africa is urgently needed (FEWSNET, 2019).

EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Using an integrated method consisting of a stochastic method and a computable general equilibrium model, Solaymani (2018) examined the short term and long-term effects of the likely simultaneous change in rainfall and temperature on food availability and access issues in Malaysia. The study's findings demonstrated that rainfall-temperature variability has a negative impact on food availability and access to food in both time periods because it reduces the supply of agricultural products, puts pressure on commodity inflation, and lowers household income.

The effects of climate change and variability on Honduran food security were examined by Keller *et al.* (2018). The study evaluated the resilience of food systems in ten Honduran communities in the context of climate change using a more comprehensive systems approach. The study's findings showed that a solid grasp of how communities obtain food and how climate impacts can ripple through various foods system components is essential to resilience building.

In their study, Akhtar and Masud (2022) investigated how climate factors affected the production of rice, cereals, vegetables, coffee, and agricultural value added in Malaysia. The study used the generalized method of moments (GMM) estimator on data from 1985 to 2016 and found that energy consumption and temperature had a negative and significant impact on the production of rice and vegetables, while rainfall, temperature, the use of fossil fuels, and humidity had an insignificant effect on the production of cereals.

Kaur (2017) used a Cobb Douglas production function included-model to simulate the effects of climate change on Indian agriculture and food security. The study's conclusions demonstrated that India's agriculture and food security are severely impacted by climate change.

Using the ordinary least squares technique, Ajay and Pritee (2013) examined how climate change affected India's food security, agricultural productivity in terms of quantity, and the monetary value of production. The study's conclusions demonstrated that India's agricultural output and food security are significantly impacted negatively by climate change.

Mahinda, Radin Firdaus, and Shamila (2021) investigated Sri Lanka's food security and climate change by employing a narrative review methodology. The study's main conclusions demonstrated that climate change has a negative influence on global food security, increasing poverty, hunger, and malnutrition, all of which disproportionately affect emerging countries, the poor, and marginalized people.

Ayo, Omosebi, and Sulieman (2014) studied the effect of climate change on the Nigeria's economy, using comparative analytical method of analysis. The findings of the study identified the following: reduced productivity of agriculture, variations in the patterns of precipitation and land's suitability for producing crops, changes in planting and harvesting period, improved rate of irrigation, increased pests and risks to fishes, reduced land arability, and high rate of organism's pathogenicity, and contamination of aflatoxin as the effects of climate change in Nigeria.

In their study of impact of climate change on the economy of Nigeria, Egwuabor and Egwuchukwu (2017) employed ordinary least squares method, with scope of the study ranging from 2014 to 2016. Gross domestic product was used as a proxy for economic growth (dependent variable of the study), climate change which was proxied by average rainfall, forest depletion, and carbon emission; government expenditure, domestic private investment, and average official exchange rate were introduced as independent variables. The study found that economy of Nigeria has been negatively affected by the climate change over the timeframe of the study. Though the study formed a robust model for estimation of data, it failed to adopt a more effective proxy for economic growth, like gross domestic product growth rate or real gross domestic product. The study also suffered from lack of theoretical framework. Again, the introduction of autoregressive distributed lag technique would have been more suitable than ordinary least squares method; considering the different order of integration found in the unit root test of the study.

Ajay and Pritee (2018) conducted a conceptual study on the impact of climatic and non-climatic variables on food security of developing countries using the literature review method. In the measurement of food security, several approaches were suggested including binary dimensional technique, per capita food deficit method, principle component analysis, per capita food expenditure, composite Z-score method, per capita calories food intake availability, and per capita food grain availability. At the individual level, the study adopted calories intake approach as the most significant. The findings of the study showed that accessibility, availability, utilization, and stability were significantly related with food security in the developing countries. Also, it was shown that climatic variations have a negative significant effect on food security in developing countries. However, due to limited literature on the impact of climatic changes on food security, lack of theoretical framework, and econometric analytical approach; the result of the study could not be competently held for future prediction.

Adesete, Olanubi, and Dauda (2022) studied the impact of climate change on food security in thirty selected sub-Saharan African countries. The study adopted generalized methods of moment technique for data analysis, and employed food supply, food security, gross domestic per capita income, inflation rate, and population growth as its variables. The findings of the study indicated that climate change has a significant negative effect on food security in the selected sub-Saharan African countries.

Idumah, Mangodo, Ighodaro, and Owombo (2016) examined the impact of climate change on food production in Nigeria with the use of vector error correction technique. Employing secondary data from 1975 to 2010, the study adopted agricultural output, relative humidity, temperature, and rainfall as its variables. The study concluded that rainfall has a significant positive relationship with food production in Nigeria. However, non-identification of climate change with a particular variable for proxy looks so ambiguous and complicating in terms of assessing climate change impact as the anchor independent variable.

Brenya, Jiang, Sampene, and Zhu (2024) looked into how nutrition, innovation, the circular economy, and climate change influenced family food security in Sub-Saharan African countries. Panel data were analyzed using cointegration and the Granger causality test in the study, utilizing fixed and random effect modeling. The study's conclusions demonstrated that households' efforts to attain food security are hampered by climate change, which has the opposite effect on policymaking.

Cui and Zhong (2024) used a moving-average specification approach to study the influenced agricultural modifications in response to long-term climate change in China. The farmland area, temperature, and precipitation are the study's variables. The study's findings showed that whereas long-term rises in precipitation level enhance farmland in dry regions but lower it in humid regions, long-term increases in temperature level boost cropland in cold regions but reduce it in hot ones.

Using the instrumental variable generalized method of moment technique, Dimnwobi, Okere, Onuoha, and Ekeseobi (2022) evaluated the link between energy poverty, environmental degradation, and agricultural output in 35 Sub-Saharan African countries. The study's conclusions demonstrated that, although energy poverty had a considerable positive impact, ecological footprint had a major adverse effect on agricultural output in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Following the literature review technique, Dauda (2023) investigated the relationship between climate change and food security in Nigeria between 2010 and 2020. From its findings, Nigeria's agricultural output, nutritional outcomes, and food insecurity are severely impacted by climate change.

The influence of climate change on food security in Tanzania was examined by Arndt, Farnier, Strzepek, and Thurlow (2011) using a dynamic computable general equilibrium modeling approach. The study's findings demonstrated that Tanzania's food security is negatively impacted by climate change.

Sambo and Sule (2023) investigated the impact of climate change on food production and security in Northern Nigeria. In analyzing its data, the study involved the use of documentation, and thematic analytical interpretations. The study's conclusions demonstrated how Northern Nigeria's escalating food security crisis undermines the nation's socio-economic and political structures, leading to conflicts between ethnic and religious groups, mass migration, starvation, illnesses, and nutritional deficiencies.

The implications of climate change on food security and the subsequent health consequences of undernourishment on expectant mothers and new-borns during the perinatal period were investigated by Hadley, Talbott, Sanjana Reddy, and Wheat (2023). The study, which made use of literature review technique, found that food security and the health of expectant mothers and their unborn children are negatively impacted by climate change.

With a non-linear auto-regressive distributive lag technique, Khurshid and Abid (2024) investigated the asymmetrical impacts of political globalization and environmental shifts on food security in Pakistan. The study's conclusions showed a negative correlation between environmental changes and political globalization and food security.

Employing the panel corrected standard error technique, Hamadjoda, Asare-Nuamah, Njong, Kondowe, and Musakaruka (2024) examined how climate variability affected food security in Sub-

Saharan Africa. The empirical findings indicated that while temperature has a negative correlation with food security, precipitation and CO₂ emissions have a favourable impact.

Applying a dynamic panel and the Generalized Method of Moments technique, Sabola (2024) examined how climate change is affecting agricultural commerce and food security in developing nations, with a particular emphasis on Southern Africa. The study discovered that trade in agricultural products is significantly harmed by climate change.

Oyelami, Edewor, Folorunso, and Abasilim (2023) examined the relationship between food security, institutional quality, and climatic change in sub-Saharan Africa with ordinary least squares method. The study's findings demonstrated that food security is significantly improved by climate change.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

In line with the objective of this study; the researcher adopts food security framework of Food and Agricultural Organization (2009). The functional model of the food security framework is stated thus:

$$\text{Food Security} = f(\text{Climatic factors, Governance, Economic issues, Demographic matters}),\dots,(3.1)$$

Transforming the functional model of the FAO to incorporate relevant variables of this study, equation (3.1) is restructured thus:

$$\text{Food Security} = f(\text{Climate Change, Government Agricultural Expenditure, Food Price Inflation, Population Growth rate, } Z_t)\dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

Where; Climate change represents Climatic factors, Government Agricultural Expenditure represents Governance, Food Price Inflation represents Economic issues, Population Growth rate represents Demographic matters, and Climate change represents Climatic factors as expressed in equation (3.1); while Z_t represents other variables that influenced food security but were not captured in equation (3.2).

Based on equation (3.2), and other relevant independent variables of food security, the model of the study is specified thus:

$$\text{FS} = f(\text{CLC,POPGR,FEXP,FPINF,GQ,AGINF})\dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

Where;

FS = Food Security using Global Food Security Index as a proxy

CLC = Climate Change

POPGR = Population Growth Rate

FEXP = Food Export

FPINFR = Food Price Inflation Rate

GQ = Governance Quality proxied with Corruption Perception Index

AGINF = Agricultural Infrastructure

Modifying equation (3.3) into econometric model showed that:

$$\text{FS}_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2\text{CLC}_t + \beta_3\text{POPGR}_t + \beta_4\text{LOGFEXP}_t + \beta_5\text{FPINF}_t + \beta_6\text{GQ}_t + \beta_7\text{LOGAGINF}_t + \mu_t$$

..... (3.4)

3.3 Source of Data

Various data and their sources as employed in this study are shown in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Description of Data

Series	Description	Unit of Measurement	Apriori Expectation	Source
FS	Food Security proxied with Global Food Security Index.	Index number		World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank
CLC	Climate change represented with precipitation variation.	Millimeters (mm)	Negative	World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank
POPGR	Population growth rate	Percentage (%)	Positive	National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)
FEXP	Food Export.	Naira	Negative	National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)
FPINFR	Food Price Inflation Rate.	Percentage (%)	Negative	Statistical Bulletins of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) for various years.
GQ	Governance quality proxied with Corruption Perceptions Index.	Index number	Positive	Transparency International Databank.
AGINF	Agricultural Infrastructure.	Units	Positive	World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank

Note: The quarterly data was derived from extrapolation method.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Unit Root Test

To assess the impact of climate change on food security in Nigeria, the study first conducts a unit root test on all the variables used. This initial test is essential to prevent the risk of obtaining misleading regression results. Furthermore, it ensures that all data are analyzed at their stationary levels, enhancing the reliability and robustness of the findings for accurate analysis and forecasting.

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test Result for ADF.

Variables	ADF Test Value	T-Statistic @ 5%	Prob. Value	Order of Integration	Interpretation
D(CLC)	-4.4302	-2.8829	0.0004	I(1)	No unit root at 1st Difference
D(FPINFR)	-3.5385	-2.8829	0.0084	I(1)	No unit root at 1st Difference
D(LOGFEXP)	-2.9768	-2.8829	0.0397	I(1)	No unit root at 1st Difference
D(GQ)	-3.1851	-2.8823	0.0230	I(1)	No unit root at 1st Difference
D(FS,2)	-25.2226	-2.8823	0.0000	I(2)	No unit root at 2nd Difference
D(LOGAGINF,2)	-8.5863	-2.8829	0.0000	I(2)	No unit root at 2nd Difference
D(POPGR,2)	-11.8853	-2.8818	0.0000	I(2)	No unit root at 2nd Difference

Source: E-views Output.

The Schwartz Information Criterion was used to establish the lag truncations for the ADF unit root test. The variables Climate Change (CLC), Food Price Inflation Rate (FPINFR), Food Exports (FEXP), and Governance Quality (GQ) are all integrated of order one, or {I(1)}, as indicated in Table 4.1. This means that at their first difference, they are all unit root-free. On the other hand, the variables Population Growth Rate (POPGR), Agricultural Infrastructure (AGINF), and Food Security (FS) are integrated of order two, represented by the symbol {I(2)}, meaning they reach stationarity at their second difference. These findings imply that in order to prevent spurious regression and guarantee accurate forecasting, all variables should only be used at their stationary levels.

Test of Hypothesis

To achieve the objective of this study, the null hypothesis that Climate change has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria is tested.

Table 4.2. Climate Change and Food Security in Nigeria.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
CLC	-2.8086	1.088134	-2.5811	0.0098
POPGR	-63.4940	4.115678	-15.4274	0.0000
LOGFEXP	-0.1092	0.092528	-1.1800	0.2380
FPINFR	-0.0213	0.022521	-0.9453	0.3445
GQ	-0.9490	0.435562	-2.1788	0.0293
LOGAGINF	0.0053	0.000192	27.4575	0.0000
C	136.6738	10.1878	13.4154	0.0000

Source: E-views Output.

With a coefficient value of -2.8086 for the CLC series, Table 4.11 shows that climate change has a significant negative effect on food security in Nigeria. Additionally, since the probability value for the CLC series (0.009) is less than 5%, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis that climate change in Nigeria has a significant negative effect on food security. Similarly, population growth (POPGR), food exports (LOGFEXP), food price inflation rate (FPINFR), and governance quality (GQ) also have negative effects on food security in Nigeria. In contrast, only agricultural infrastructure (AGINF) exhibits a positive effect on food security in Nigeria.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study show that climate change has a negative impact on food security in Nigeria. This result, which aligns with the study's apriori expectations, corroborates the findings of Arndt, Farner, Strzepek, and Thurlow (2011), Adesete, Olanubi, and Dauda (2022), and Dauda (2023). The study also reveals that food security declines by roughly 3 units for every unit increase in climate change. By decreasing agricultural productivity, the destructive effects of floods, droughts, and other climate shocks lead to a significant decline in food security. Over the past few decades, annual precipitation fluctuations and trends in Nigeria have exhibited inter-annual variations that have triggered extreme weather events such as droughts and floods in various regions. These events have caused the loss of livestock and crop yields, thereby jeopardizing Nigeria's food security. Climate change also negatively impacts natural resources, reducing their capacity to provide essential agricultural products, which are critical for human consumption and serve as the primary source of livelihood and income for most Nigerian farmers. There is also a growing public concern that Nigeria's already high level of food insecurity is being worsened by climate change, which is causing displacement in several States. Agrarian communities living in areas where unchecked resource depletion has led to climate-induced land degradation are particularly vulnerable to the instability caused by climate change. Therefore, the Nigerian government must urgently implement policies and activities to reduce the vulnerability of Nigeria's agricultural sector to climate change, while also improving adaptation and mitigation measures. These efforts are crucial for increasing the nation's food production, achieve food sufficiency, and attain the overall goal of food security.

In the same vein, population growth (POPGR), food exports (LOGFEXP), food price inflation (FPINFR), and governance quality (GQ) were found to be negatively related with food security in Nigeria. The negative impact of population growth on food security indicates that as population continues to grow, the demand for food also improves thereby exerting much pressure on the available food in the country. As the demand for limited food is pressured, scarcity of food and food price inflation exacerbated thereby leading to food insecurity in Nigeria. The current trend of quest for food exports as a means of economic diversification reduce available food for domestic consumption, thereby worsening food insecurity as can be shown in the result of negative impact of food exports on food security in Nigeria. Also, food price inflation reduces the purchasing power of Nigerian consumers, thereby making it difficult for individuals to access quality foods for consumption which impedes food security as can be seen from the negative relationship between food price inflation and food security in our findings. Ineffective policy

implementation, resource allocation, and institutional structure are indication of poor quality governance which has failed to improve food availability and accessibility in Nigeria based on the negative effect of governance quality on food security in the findings of the study.

On the other hand, only agricultural infrastructure (AGINF) indicates a positive impact on food security in Nigeria from the findings of the study. This shows the imperative of investments in agricultural infrastructure like irrigational facilities and farm roads to boost food production and distribution efficiency. Agricultural infrastructure development leads to higher output, reduced post-harvest losses, improved market access, thereby influencing food security positively in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations:

- i. **Adoption of climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies:** the significant negative impact of climate change on food security justifies the need for adoption of climate change mitigation and adaptation measures for sustainable agriculture. Government agricultural policies should be targeted at climate resilient agricultural practices such as, adoption of flood-resistant varieties of crops, improved irrigational facilities, and dry season farming system to mitigate the effect of climate change.
- ii. **Population control measures:** the need for adoption and implementation of effective population control measures is underscored by the negative impact of population growth on food security as shown in this study. Therefore, government should promote the policies of family planning, education, and sensitization programmes to control population explosion and align same with the existing availability of foods in the country.
- iii. **Regulating food export to maintain sustainable food sufficiency:** though food exports attracts foreign exchange and contributes to economic growth, it is obvious from our findings that excessive reliance on food export has a detrimental effect of food security in Nigeria. Thus, government agricultural policies that promote value addition on for exportable products should be adopted, to improve export earnings as well as maintaining domestic food supply via trade regulations and strategic food reserves.
- iv. **Stable food price control measures:** to improve access to food, the need for adoption of food price control policies to stabilize the prices of food through improved agricultural production, investment in agricultural infrastructure, and food subsidies is underscored. This is necessitated based on the negative impact of food price inflation on food security as observed from the outcome of this study.
- v. **Improving governance quality and institutional structure:** since governance quality has shown to be negatively impacted on food security, there is need for improved public policy implementation, transparency and accountability in governance. Also, to achieve resource allocation efficiency and effectiveness of public policies, the need to strengthen institutional structure and reduce corruption should be emphasized by the government.
- vi. **Sustainable agricultural infrastructure investment:** considering the positive effect of agricultural infrastructure on food security in Nigeria from the findings of this study, the government should prioritise investment in agricultural infrastructure like irrigational facilities, storage facilities, post-harvest technologies, and feeder roads to continue boosting food security in Nigeria.

In conclusion, addressing food security problems in Nigeria needs divergent measures including climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies; population control policies, food export regulation policies, food price control measures, improved governance quality, and sustainable agricultural infrastructure development. Adopting and implementing these policy measures will assist mitigate the negative impact of climate change and other explanatory variables, thereby improving food security in Nigeria.

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